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Artificial intelligence for automatic optical inspection of multilayered solid oxide membranes

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Abstract

Large scale implementation of SOFC technology for chemical-to-electrical energy conversion is limited by the high cost of systems per kW power. Production of the SOFC MEA's is the major part of the system cost. This price component can be substantially reduced through scale up, automation, and optimization of the manufacturing process. Mass production requires automatic quality control methods to reliably detect functional defects early in the production cycle to improve production yield, and the long-term stability and reliability of the final stacks.

Defects ranging in size from mm to few microns, randomly located on the ionic conductive membrane, push the limits of conventional imaging hardware and challenge reliability and productivity of classical algorithms for visual data analysis. Artificial Intelligence (AI) offers a much higher degree of freedom for feature detection and classification. Besides this, it is more suited to work with large amounts of data than classical algorithms. Currently, AI implemented on commercially available hardware has been exploited by Google and Tesla in self-driving cars. This makes AI-based systems a viable option for cost-effective real-time smart quality control.

In this study we evaluate the feasibility of detection and classification of defects in fired SOFC membranes with a custom-developed AI system. The optical inspection was developed for high-speed imaging of solid oxide membranes at 3.5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ resolution in a production environment with 100% inspection. The high-resolution images of SOFC plates were used for automated recognition of 3 dimensional defects like craters, hairs, cracks and pinholes down to 10 micrometer in size. The developed system demonstrates highly improved rates of correct defect detection compared to conventional vision systems at an unprecedented speed and is very promising for cost reduction of SOFC systems.

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Introduction

Regulation of CO₂ emission and transition toward sustainable energy sources call for reliable and efficient technology for energy conversion and storage. Solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC) are an example of such a technology, which can be used for both centralized and distributed applications. However, a substantial reduction of price per kW power and a guaranteed long-term stability of fuel cell stacks are needed to enable their large-scale implementation. This can be achieved through automation and implementation of reliable quality control at different steps of the ceramic membrane's production. Typical 3 dimensional imperfections as holes, pinholes, scratches, and cracks can compromise gas impermeability and/or electrical isolation between cathode and anode sides of individual SOFC membranes. These defects are distinguishable by humans when illuminated by visible-light under a correct angle which allows the use of commercial hardware to capture visual information in a digital form. Detection and classification of the defects present in the ceramic material can then be achieved by means of classical image analysis techniques [1-2]. However, development of algorithm for reliable classification of these features with classical image analysis techniques can be very challenging. For example, holes and bumps or cracks and fibers consist of similar features which leads to misidentification of these structures and can cause a large number of false-positives or low detection rates. More reliable classification of such defects would require more nuanced multi-parameter description of these features which is almost impossible to design and describe 'by hand'. Besides that, characteristic sizes of some functional defects are about tens micrometers resulting in large amounts of data at the required magnifications. Processing of the data with classical algorithms within the limited time for real time 100 % production inspection can be extremely challenging and costly as they are CPU-intensive. An alternative to classical image analysis techniques is using neural networks-based (NNs) artificial intelligence. In the last years, NNs have seen very rapid development for natural language analysis (e.g. translation, voice-to-text conversion, human-machine communication), image and video processing (e.g. detection and classification of objects, alteration and generation of visual data), autonomous operation of vehicles (e.g. self-driving cars) [3-4]. This progress is mainly thanks to substantial development of Graphical Processing Units (GPUs), containing thousands processing cores which allow for mass-parallel data processing.

Figure 1. An illustration of an artificial neural network: data inputs, data outputs, and a number of hidden interconnected layers.

Very often NNs outperform classical analysis algorithms in visual data analysis due the large number of parameters which are taken into account for decision making. These parameters – or in other words elementary data analysis algorithms – compose so-called hidden layers that are connected via artificial neurons into a complicated grid, called an artificial neural network (Figure 1). This internal structure of a NN is key for processing and/or analysis of the input data which can be done at superhuman level. However, such a system, which may contain hundreds of hidden layers, cannot be easily described by a developer and, because of this, a so-called supervised learning is used to train the network for analysis and/or processing of particular types of data.

In this study, we implemented custom artificial NNs for detection and classification of functional defects present in fired SOFC membranes. The entire surface of every membrane was scanned with the magnification of 3.5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ which resulted in an image of up to 2 gigapixel per sample. This visual data was used to train a range of custom NNs which were later used for detection and classification of five categories of functional defects in this product. Analysis of images was carried out on the fly with a multi-node processing unit in order to meet cycle time below 10 s per sample needed for automatic optical inspection (AOI) of SOFC membranes produced on a large scale. The data analysis algorithms were implemented in a standalone AOI unit for SOFC inspection.

1. Scientific Approach

The project started with evaluation and comparison of commercial solutions for visible-light imaging and processing of visual data. The most suitable equipment was shortlisted and used for the development of a prototype AOI system. A platform for the NN development was selected based on previous experience. A multi-node computing unit with processing power in the order of 100 TFlops was designed and built.

After installation and integration of the imaging hardware, an illumination system was developed to yield the required contrast and luminosity. Five different categories of functional defects – the defects that compromise gas impermeability and structural integrity of the SOFC membranes in short and long-term – were identified in these images. The electrolyte layer of a sufficiently large number of fired SOFC membranes was scanned by this setup. Functional defects were labeled on the resulting images. This data set was used for training and development of NNs architectures.

Predictions of the trained NNs were evaluated with a separate test data set. The networks with the highest detection rates were further trained with an extended data set containing more examples of defects for which predictions were below the required level. The factors influencing data processing time (i.e. CPU, GPU, and RAM clock speed; data read, write, and transfer bandwidth) were analyzed and the code was further optimized to fully utilize available hardware resources. The option for a simple system expansion by multiple processing units and real-time sharing of processing power has been developed in the software stack to allow scalability of the AOI system.

2. Experiments

2.1 Illumination. The system development started with optimization of the illumination system. Performance of several commercial systems was compared. However, large effective f-numbers of the imaging system (due to high magnification ratios) resulted in very low light intensity at the digital camera sensor. In order to meet the target scanning speed, we developed in-house a high-brightness illumination system that allows detection of the 3-D defects on a low contrast surface. The influence of illumination geometry and

spectral properties of the light source on visualization of functional defects present in the electrolyte layer of fired SOFC membranes was evaluated with this in-house developed system.

2.2 Data set. A sufficiently large number of fired SOFC cells of different product types and production batches were scanned at the resolution of 3.5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$. Five categories of functional defects were identified and labeled in the digital images. The resulting set of labeled images was used for supervised training of custom NNs with different architectures. Intensity and angle of incident light were varied in the range expected for industrial systems in order to improve robustness of the AOI system.

2.3 Neural network design. The large area of each SOFC membranes (ca. 250 cm^2) made us decide to use rather large images for both training and detection of defects. This was done to avoid multiple counts of functional defects at the edges and in the corners of images. Both of them are rather difficult to mitigate during data analysis. On the other hand, training and inference with large images required computing units equipped with sufficient amount of memory. No image compression can be used as it would compromise detection of small features. Therefore, we developed a number of custom NNs with different structure, size, and functionality of deeper layers to improve the detection results and foremost to increase speed.

2.4 Extension of the data set. Custom NNs were trained with the same data set and their performance was cross-compared. Detection accuracy was determined per category of functional defects. For the categories, in which NNs demonstrated low accuracy, the training data set was further extended with additional examples of these features.

3. Results

3.1 Illumination geometry and wavelength. Visualization of functional defects in the thin translucent layer of fired SOFC membranes was complicated by similar optical properties of the electrolyte (YSZ) and anode (NiO–YSZ cermet) layers. Although sufficiently high contrast may be expected, when a light source with longer wavelength is used to illuminate fired SOFC membranes containing green-tinted NiO, we did not observe any substantial difference between white and long wavelength illumination. This can be explained by the fact that green color of NiO arises from a weak d-d transition [5]. Moreover, both the anode and electrolyte layers contain YSZ which results in similar reflectivity of these layers.

Figure 2. Examples of surface features present in the electrolyte layer of fired SOFC membranes. Functional defects: large (a) and small (b) holes, pattern of burnt-out fiber (c), crack (d), contamination (f). Non-functional defects: bump (e). Tiles (a) – (e) have total size of 350 μm ; tile (f) – 1.2 mm.

Therefore, we optimized illumination geometry to improve visualization of functional defects present in the fired electrolyte layer. Single sided illumination of SOFC membranes at relatively low angle was found to deliver the highest contrast. This illumination geometry exaggerates surface 3D features of membranes' surface. Transitions from highlight to shadows were crucial for discrimination between functional defects (i.e. holes, cracks, other piercings, and contaminations in the electrolyte layer) and irregularities of the oxide layer's height. Examples of functional and non-functional defects are shown in Figure 2.

3.2 Detection accuracy. The early builds of our NNs had high detection rates for holes larger than 50 μm , while detection of small pinholes was less reliable. Detection of linear defects (cracks and fibers) was rather low as well. This was due to lower abundance of linear defects in the investigated samples as compared with holes. Therefore, detection of linear defects was substantially improved after retraining of the NNs with the extended data set containing more examples of linear defects. On the other hand, accurate detection of small holes could be achieved only when the structure and functionality of hidden layers was redesigned fully. A similar solution was required to improve recognition of large numbers of defects aggregated on small surface areas. Resulting trained network showed very high detection accuracy of functional defects but were insensitive to other features. For instance, Figure 3 shows that a NN was not triggered by a prominent bump while other imperfections were properly detected.

3.3 Detection time. With our optimal NN configuration a complete analysis – i.e. detection and classification of 5 categories of functional defects – of one segment of an SOFC membrane requires only 25 ms. This means that a complete optical inspection of a fired SOFC membrane can take less than the required 10 s. However, due overheads for data transfer, handling, and manipulation multiple, simultaneous node analysis is required to meet the speed targets for a real-time production inspection. A multi-node computing unit was successfully set-up and optimized for parallel analysis of visual data, while image

acquisition was handled by a separate frame grabbing unit. This kept different processing tasks from interfering with each other.

Moreover, such a modular system is more flexible, scalable, adaptable, and upgradable in comparison with an all-in-one mainframe approach. A high-speed low-latency fiber optics-based network interface implemented in this AOI system allows us to separate image acquisition and data processing units from each other in harsh industrial environment.

The software stack was developed around the concept allowing the data acquisition unit(s) to book available computing nodes of the data processing unit(s) and schedule analysis tasks in real time. This allows for parallel data processing and maximizes utilization of the processing power. Moreover, as the total processing time for our system linearly decreases with the increasing of the number of computing nodes, such a neural network-based system can be implemented for fast and reliable automatic visual inspection of SOFC membranes as well as other products of different size.

Figure 3. Example of detection and classification of functional defects performed with a trained NN. Note a bump in the right part of the image that was ignored by the system.

4. Conclusions

The results of this work demonstrate that customized neural networks are a robust tool for accurate real-time optical inspection of SOFC. The ability of artificial NNs to extract very complicated features from the images can be utilized for reliable categorization of objects present in inspected material. Trained NNs can discriminate between defects and features which do not have adverse effect on performance of the system which is crucial to avoiding false-positives. Moreover, scalability of such NN-based AOI-systems makes them suitable for mass manufacturing where short operation cycles and reliability of detection are a must.

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References

- [1] P. Gamage and S. Q. Xie A real-time vision system for defect inspection in cast extrusion manufacturing process. The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology 40, 144, 2009
- [2] G. M. Atiqur Rahaman and Md. Mobarak Hossain Automatic Defect Detection and Classification Technique from Image: A Special Case Using Ceramic Tiles 1, 22, 2009
- [3] M. Chang et al. Development of an optical inspection platform for surface defect detection in touch panel glass. International Journal of Optomechatronics 40, 63, 2016
- [4] <https://spectrum.ieee.org/cars-that-think/transportation/self-driving/driveai-brings-deep-learning-to-selfdriving-cars> accessed on 15-May-2018
- [5] R. Newman and R. M. Chrenko Optical Properties of Nickel Oxide. Physical Review 114, 1507, 1959